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D7.3. Internal report on scenario outputs for long-term assessment regarding climate change resilience, productivity, and environmental impacts

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I. Executive summary

Analyses of the historical weather data from 2018 to 2022 in the Niakhar region have revealed irregular patterns characterized by alternating periods of both low and high annual precipitation. This unpredictable variation underscores the importance of carefully evaluating future climate projections to make well-informed decisions regarding future agricultural systems and food production strategies. Future climate projection anomalies of precipitation and air temperature for the Niakhar region used for this assessment were obtained from the global climate model (GCM) compilations of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Projects (CMIP6), which form the data foundation of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessment Reports.

The modeled precipitation and air temperature were based on the compilation of outcomes of multi-model ensemble (MME) simulations, representing the spectrum and distribution of the most feasible projected changes in the climate system at a monthly spatial resolution. Two shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) climate scenarios, SSP-1.91 and 8.5 for the periods 2020–2039 (near future) and 2080–2099 (far future) were used for this report.

The model scenarios presented in this report (D7.3) centered on diverse management and land-use systems, specifically focusing on the Niakhar MARP report (VWP2) and outcomes of innovation platform (IP) meetings where partners have implemented crop–shrub–livestock (CSL) systems. In summary, soil amendment systems involving locally available organic resources (e.g. *Guiera s.* biomass, cow dung manure), mineral fertilizer, and their mixture applied to Millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) - Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) intercropping systems. In addition, varying planting densities of *Guiera s.* under pruning practices of managed residue and no residue retention were intercropped with Millet.

These CSL systems were chosen based on their capacity to improve the efficiency of resource utilization, such as biomass production, grain yields, nutrient cycling, and soil organic C accumulation. Moreover, the selected CSL systems are expected to improve resilience to various stresses, such as limited water availability, and rising temperatures. These scenarios were run under the Niakhar historical weather conditions and the projected future climate scenarios of the Niakhar region for ten years using the Land Use Change Impact Assessment (LUCIA) model.

The simulations showed that Millet AGB and grain yield production increased in the long-term under sole organic soil amendments and their combination with mineral fertilizer compared to sole mineral fertilization. This was associated with a decline in SOM under mineral fertilizer-managed soils during the ten-year simulation period. With regard to climate change, a strong negative impact on millet yield, particularly during drought years and the more severe SSP-8.5 scenario was simulated under the longer-term climate trends.

The simulated AGB of *Guiera s.* increased under the high planting density. Almost all the future climate scenarios decreased the AGB growth of *Guiera s.* compared to the historical, especially SSP-8.5 (2080-2099). Over the course of the ten-year simulation, SOM increased with increasing *Guiera s.* planting density for every climate scenario. The positive contribution of residue retention to SOM was only visible under historical conditions. The reasons for these impacts need further investigations.

2. Introduction

This is the third output of Work Package 7 (D7.3). It extends the findings of the initial two reports (D7.1 and D7.2), which presented a comprehensive overview of existing crops, cropping systems, soil types, land use, and tree and shrub cover at a broader scale. Subsequently, these findings served as a baseline for parameterizing and calibrating the LUCIA model. The objective of this report is to evaluate stakeholder scenario outputs under long-term climate projections (climate change scenarios). Thus, model scenarios involving CLS systems, which have the capability to enhance resource use efficiency (e.g. biomass production and yields) and withstand climate change (e.g., productivity under water and temperature constraints), were examined to assess their effects on food production and environmental resources (SOM, soil, and vegetation carbon stocks). Niakhar watershed in Senegal was used as the study site for this assessment. The Sob sub-catchment was used for detailed modelling activities as the presence of the IRD Faidherbia flux experimental site provided detailed historical weather and crop data (2018-2022). The climate projection data for Niakhar was obtained from the global climate model compilations of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Projects (CMIP6). These projection data are displayed as multi-model ensembles, which depict the range and distribution of the most plausible projected changes in the climate system under two shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs): the optimistic scenario SSP1-1.9 (global CO₂ emissions cut to net zero around 2050) and the high emission scenario SSP5-8.5 (limited policy intervention) assessed in the near (2020–2039) and far (2080–2099) future.

3. Climate change monitoring

Climate variations constantly pose a continuous threat to the environment and have the potential to result in substantial economic losses. The crucial importance of long-term climate monitoring lies in gaining insights into historical changes in both global and local climates. Moreover, historical climate observations play a vital role in advancing our understanding of the Earth's physical and dynamic processes and their impact on the environment.

3.1 Historical climate data

A five-year historical climate data for this assessment was obtained from the Faidherbia–Flux Niakhar, Sob. The Faidherbia-Flux station is operated by IRD, France of WP5 led by Dr. Olivier Roupsard. The Faidherbia flux site is equipped with eddy covariance antennas designed to monitor radiation, energy, and GHG fluxes over the whole ecosystem, and fluxes below tree crowns (from soil and crops). Meteorological data was provided by an automatic station (CRI000, Campbell Sci.) equipped with classical sensors. Measured parameters included air temperature and relative humidity (CS215, 2 m), wind speed (WindMaster sonic anemometer (Gill Instruments, Lymington, UK), 4.5 m and estimation at 2 m), and rainfall (TE25MM) (Diongue et al., 2022). Recordings of rainfall and air temperature data from the Faidherbia–Flux were averaged to obtain representative daily and monthly data for five years (2018–2022).

Over the course of five years, the yearly rainfall displayed variations in precipitation levels, with some periods experiencing lower and others with higher amounts of rainfall. The recorded yearly precipitation ranged from 454 to 822 mm, with an average of 574 mm (Fig. 1a). Throughout the crop–growing season (May–October), the monthly rainfall distribution varied from 11 to 224 mm across the five years (Fig. 1b). Notably, there was a significant rise in rainfall from May to August, followed by a notable decline from September to October. The months of August and September stood out as having particularly high rainfall (indicated by the purple rectangle).

Figure 1. Historical (2018–2022) precipitation at the Faidherbia Flux site, Niakhar, Senegal: a) cumulative annual precipitation; b) monthly precipitation for the crop growing season (May–October).

3.2 Projected climate anomaly in the Niakhar region

The climate projection data for the Niakhar region was obtained from the global climate model (GCM) compilations of the Coupled Model Inter-comparison Projects (CMIP6), which form the data foundation of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Assessment Reports (<https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/senegal/climate-data-projections-general>). The displayed modeled precipitation and air temperature were based on the compilation of outcomes of multi-model ensembles (MME) simulations, representing the spectrum and distribution of the most feasible projected changes in the climate system. Projection data is presented at a monthly gridded $1.0^\circ \times 1.0^\circ$ (100km x 100km) spatial resolution. The period 1995–2014 was designated as the reference period, and the period 2020–2039 (near future) and 2080–2099 (far future) were considered the future for this report under two Shared Socioeconomics Pathway (SSP) climate scenarios. The SSP-1.9 scenario is characterized by an exceptionally low forcing level, with emission levels rapidly reduced to zero and an extended period of negative CO_2 emissions (O'Neill et al., 2016). Conversely, the SSP-8.5 scenario aims to stabilize radiative forcing at 8.5 Wm^{-2} by the year 2100, indicating a high radiative forcing scenario.

The precipitation anomalies exhibited a combination of positive and negative trends during the crop-growing season for both SSPs (Fig. 2). Notably, significant changes in precipitation are anticipated in the months of July, August, and September. For SSP-8.5, there is an expected decline in precipitation during June, July, and August in both the near and far future, with August experiencing the most substantial average reduction of 30 mm in the far future. SSP-1.9 also

projected a reducing trend in precipitation in the far future in June, July, and August. On the other hand, under SSP-1.9 (near future), positive anomalies are projected for June, July, and September, with a notable increase of 10 mm in precipitation in September. Over the whole year, the projected changes amounted to +10, -13, -26, and -50 mm for SSP-1.9 (2020–2039), SSP-8.5 (2020–2039), SSP-1.9 (2080–2099) and SSP-8.5 (2080–2099) respectively. Given the large uncertainties associated with the MME rainfall projections arising from natural variability, scenarios, and climate models (IPCC 2021), the changes are relatively moderate but with little confidence.

Figure 2. Projected future monthly precipitation anomaly for Niakhar–Senegal (Reference period: 1995–2014; SSP-1.9 and 8.5 for near (2020–2039) and far (2080–2099) future; average Multi-Model Ensemble (CMIP6) estimates).

For air temperature, both SSPs in the near and far future showed a positive change in minimum, maximum and mean temperature during the crop-growing season except in September in the near future, where maximum temperature is expected to be negative (-0.2 °C) under SSP-1.9 (Fig. 3). Under SSP-8.5 (2080–2099) minimum, maximum and mean air temperature exceeded the baseline (1995–2014) by mostly >3 °C, and the other remaining future climate projections by approximately 2 °C within the crop-growth window.

Figure 3. Projected monthly air temperature (minimum, maximum and mean) anomaly for 2020–2039, Niakhar–Senegal (Reference period: 1995–2014; SSP–1.9 and 8.5 for near (2020–2039) and far future (2080–2099); average Multi-Model Ensemble (CMIP6) estimations).

3.3 Future climate scenarios

Given that the future climate anomalies were available at a monthly-timescale resolution, the future climate scenarios were produced by applying the monthly future anomalies (2020–2039) and (2080–2099) of the MME for SSP-1.9 and SSP-8.5 against the five-year average monthly historical observations of Niakhar.

The projected precipitation under SSP-1.9 and 8.5 were closely similar to the historical five-year during May, June, and October, wherein the monthly cumulative precipitation remained below 50 mm (Fig. 4). During July, a significant portion of the precipitation is anticipated in SSP-1.9 (2020–2039), while SSP-8.5 (2080–2099) is projected to have lower precipitation. In the months of August and September, which typically receive a substantial amount of rainfall, all the future climate scenarios demonstrated reduced precipitation in comparison to historical patterns, particularly evident in SSP-8.5 (2080–2099) during August. In September, only the near future SSPs indicated slight increases in precipitation compared to the historical conditions.

Figure 4. Annual cycle of precipitation for the historical period (2018–2022), the near (2020–2039) and far future (2080–2099) under SSP-1.9 and SSP-8.5 averaged over the Niakhar region on a monthly timescale.

Air temperature under the projected scenarios (SSPs) were higher than our historical climate data at the Faidherbia-Flux tower (Fig. 5). The minimum and maximum temperature under SSP-1.9 (near and far future) and SSP-8.5 (near future) were similar during the cropping season (May–October). The highest minimum, maximum and mean temperature occurred under SSP-8.5 (2080–2099) representing approximately 1.5, 1 and 1.8 °C respectively over the historical temperature. The highest mean temperature was recorded in June, July and October under SSP-

8.5 (2080–2099) indicating an approximate 1.8 °C elevation over the historical temperature (2018–2022) at the Faidherbia-Flux tower.

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Figure 5. Annual cycle of air temperature (minimum, maximum and mean) for the historical period (2018–2022) at the Faidherbia-Flux tower, as well as the near (2020–2039) and far future (2080–2099) under SSP-1.9 and SSP-8.5 averaged over the Niakhar region on a monthly timescale.

4. LUCIA model setup for scenario simulation

Referring to deliverable D7.2 (Parameterized, calibrated, and biophysically validated models), the LUCIA model has been adapted for all seven SustainSAHEL study sites. In that report, detailed model calibration and evaluation were initiated for the Niakhar site, focusing on the Sob watershed, where data from the Faidherbia flux site (WP5) were utilized to simulate and fine-tune water and hydrological processes as well as above and belowground plant growth and development. The model effectively captured observed metrics, such as aboveground biomass (AGB) and millet grain yield at maturity, with acceptable coefficient of determination, root mean square error, and Nash–Sutcliffe model efficiency. Following successful calibration, the parameterized model was employed to conduct various sensitivity analyses on specific LUCIA parameters, such as different levels of mineral and organic fertilization, and various qualities of shrub residues that can influence crop performance.

4.1 Model scenarios

The model scenarios for this report (D7.3) will concentrate on diverse management and land-use systems, specifically focusing on the Niakhar MARP report (WP2) and outcomes of the innovation platform (IP) meetings where partners have implemented crop–shrub–livestock (CSL) systems (Table 1). These CSL systems are chosen based on their potential to enhance resource use efficiency, including biomass production, grain yields, nutrient cycling (N & P uptake and losses), and soil organic C accumulation. Additionally, the selected CSL systems are expected to improve resilience to various stresses, such as limited water availability, and rising temperatures (as indicated by IPCC reports for the study site).

Five climate scenarios were created based on precipitation and air temperature. One represents the baseline (BL) precipitation and air temperature data (2018–2022) obtained from recordings by the Faidherbia–flux site in Niakhar. The others are the prolonged frequency of drought scenarios (PDF) for 2018, 2019, and 2021 by reducing precipitation and increasing air temperature based on the SSP–1.9 and 8.5 (near and far future) low and high radioactive forcing estimates for the Niakhar region. The five–year BL (historical) period was looped two times (Fig. 6). For the PDF scenarios (SSP–1.9 (2020–2039), SSP–8.5 (2020–2039), SSP–1.9 (2080–2099), and SSP–8.5 (2080–2099)), all the precipitation events in June, July, August, and September were reduced or increased according to their precipitation and air temperature anomalies (Fig. 6 and 7).

Table I. Experimental treatments at on-farm experiments in Niakhar region (Sanghaie). OF = organic fertilizer, MF = mineral fertilizer, RD = recommended dosage.

Drivers	Treatment	Description
*Soil amendment (Fertilization-adapted to local system)	i) OF: <i>Guiera s.</i> biomass (5 t ha ⁻¹) ii) OF: <i>Guiera s.</i> biomass (5 t ha ⁻¹) + MF (50% RD) iii) OF: Animal manure (5 t ha ⁻¹) iv) MF (100% RD**)	Millet intercropped with Groundnut under different organic and mineral fertilizations.
*Planting density (Density of <i>Guiera senegalensis</i>)	i) Lower (1000 plants ha ⁻¹) ii) Higher (2000 plants ha ⁻¹)	Millet intercropped with <i>Guiera s.</i> at two planting densities. Twice pruning with residue and no residue retention.
Climate regime	Baseline (typical precipitation and air temperature) Drought scenario (induced based on SSP-1.9 and 8.5 (2020–2039 and 2080–2099) projections of the study region).	2-year loop of five measured years (2018 – 2022) Precipitation events reduced and air temperature increased in years 1, 2, and 4 of the 2-year loop

* Each soil amendment and planting density will be assessed under the five-climate regimes

** RD = recommended mineral fertilization: NPK (15:10:10) is applied at 150 kg ha⁻¹ 30 days after sowing (DAS) and Urea is split applied 45 DAS at 50 kg ha⁻¹.

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Figure 6. Five-year precipitation data looped (twice) for model scenarios: a) BL (historical) precipitation based on Niakhar Faidherbia–Flux site measurements: drought scenarios with drought years in 2018, 2019, and 2021 based on: b) SSP–1.9 (2020–2039), c) SSP–8.5 (2020–2039), SSP–1.9 (2080–2099), and d) SSP–8.5 (2080–2099) projections of the Niakhar region.

Figure 7. Five-year air temperature data looped (twice) for model scenarios: a) BL (historical) air temperature based on Niakhar Faidherbia-Flux site measurements; drought scenarios with drought years in 2018, 2019, and 2021 based on: b) SSP-1.9 (2020-2039), c) SSP-8.5 (2020-2039), SSP-1.9 (2080-2099), and d) SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) projections of the Niakhar region.

4.2 Model scenario output: Soil amendment scenario

4.2.1 Plant performance under soil management and future climate

Figure 8 depicts the aboveground biomass (AGB) and grain yield of Millet across the four future climate scenarios in comparison to the recorded historical climate. In general, both AGB and grain yields changes were reduced under sole mineral fertilization (Min-Fert) in contrast to the organic amendments under each climate scenario. The progression of increasing grain yield and AGB followed the sequence: Guiera residue < Guiera residue + Min-Fert << Manure.

Regarding the climate impact, substantial reductions in AGB were observed under the SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) scenario, particularly during years with comparatively lower annual cumulative rainfall (years 1, 2, 4, 6, 7, and 9). The years 1, 2, and 4 correspond with 2018, 2019, and 2021 from the historical data respectively, and were looped twice for this simulation. With the exception of SSP-1.9 (2080-2099), all four climate scenarios indicated reductions in AGB during the fourth and ninth years compared to the historical data. Conversely, simulation years 3, 5, 8, and 10 exhibited higher AGB than the historical climate for all four climate scenarios. Interestingly, these years corresponded to periods with comparatively greater cumulative annual rainfall.

The trend in grain yield production and aboveground biomass (AGB) did not align consistently across distinct climate scenarios and soil amendments. Nevertheless, when considering the entirety of the simulated data, there was an overall reduction in grain yield across all climate scenarios in comparison to historical data, although certain exceptions were evident in the second and seventh simulation years across all soil amendments. In most of the future climate scenarios, grain yield was notably higher during the second and seventh years, except for SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) because the cumulative annual precipitation in these years were not very different across the climates. However, the reduced precipitation amount under SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) might be responsible for the reduced crop yields.

Generally, the reduced Millet grain yield performance under the climate scenarios could be attributed to the reduced rainfall and increasing air temperature. Although the effects of rainfall and temperature were not analyzed separately, their combined effect could have a counteracting effect as some of the future climate scenarios projected high rainfall within the cropping window. Nevertheless, the increasingly adverse role of higher temperatures in reducing crop yields, irrespective of rainfall changes was evident through the dynamics of AGB. It is also possible that water stress at the beginning was less severe and higher temperature led to increase in biomass. Subsequently, it became evident that water stress had a significant adverse impact on grain yield.

Sultan et al. (2013) observed in their simulation of Millet and Sorghum within the Sudanian and Sahelian agroecosystems that when the warming exceeds +2°C, the adverse effects resulting from temperature increase cannot be offset by changes in rainfall. Interestingly, our simulation only demonstrated this phenomenon in years with relatively lower annual rainfall under the SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) scenario, where the average air temperature surpassed the historical levels by about +1.8°C. The other future climate scenarios exhibited a marginal rise (0.6–0.9°C) in average air temperature compared to the historical data.

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An increase in temperature is expected to increase maintenance respiration, shorten the crop-cycle duration, and consequently decrease the growing degree-days (GDD), resulting in reduced biomass production. Likewise, the combined impacts of increased temperature and water could enhance evapotranspiration. The crop-cycle duration was increased across all the future climate scenarios compared to the historical climate (Table 2). It is important to note that while warmer temperatures might actually shorten the crop cycle, it is also possible that optimal temperature range for the crop in LUCIA was not exceeded, and so stress was not a dominant factor explaining why the climate scenarios took slightly longer to mature than the historical conditions. Among the climate scenarios, the crop-cycle duration was shorter for SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) compared to the others.

Figure 8. Simulated aboveground biomass and grain yield of Millet under future climate scenarios. The data is presented as a change relative to the historical weather data (2018-2022) of Niakhar region.

Table 2. Crop-cycle length of Millet under the historical weather (2018-2022) and future climate projections for the Niakhar region.

Simulation time (years)	Climate scenarios				
	Historical (2018-2022)	SSP-1.9 (2020-2039)	SSP-8.5 (2020-2039)	SSP-1.9 (2080-2099)	SSP-8.5 (2080-2099)
1	90	115	116	116	105
2	91	107	107	107	93
3	90	112	113	113	113
4	94	110	109	109	96
5	94	117	117	117	117
6	90	113	116	116	105
7	91	108	107	107	92
8	90	113	113	113	113
9	94	110	109	109	96
10	94	116	116	116	116
Mean	92	112	112	112	105

The average total evapotranspiration during the crop growth period (May – October) over the ten-year simulation period indicated a decline under the future climates in contrast to the historical conditions, except for the near-future SSP-1.9 scenario (Fig. 9). Notable variations in evapotranspiration were not observed across the different soil amendments for each climate scenario, which suggests that the model probably needs improvements in simulating ET_o with respect to impact of soil cover on evaporation.

Figure 9. Simulated evapotranspiration of Millet under different soil amendment and climate scenarios. Each box plot shows the cumulative evapotranspiration within the cropping season window (May–October) for ten years. The dotted horizontal lines within each box indicates the mean evapotranspiration for the ten years duration.

4.2.2 Assessing SOM and nutrient dynamics under soil management and future climates

The simulated soil organic matter (SOM) dynamics exhibited seasonal fluctuations across the various soil amendments and different climate scenarios. The ten-year dynamics demonstrated a consistent rise in SOM over time for the organic amendments across most climate scenarios (Figure 10). In contrast, the trend for Min-Fert displayed a distinct decrease in SOM, particularly under the historical and SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) climates.

In general, there was a consistent pattern of increasing SOM following the sequence: Min-Fert < Guiera residue << Guiera residue + Min-Fert <<< Manure (Figure 11c). Enhanced SOM levels were observed in the future climate scenarios compared to the historical climate. Among the different climate scenarios, SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) showed the lowest SOM, whereas SSP-1.9 (2080-2099) revealed the highest one.

When evaluating the relative changes in SOM at the end of the ten-year simulation, with respect to the SOM at the beginning, it was found that all soil amendments except Min-Fert experienced an increase in SOM (Figure 12). This indicated that SOM declined under the Min-Fert application across historical and future climates, except SSP-1.9 (2080-2099). The annual cumulative projected precipitation under SSP-1.9 (2080-2099), which was higher, compared to the other projected climates and the historical observation coupled with the low mean air temperature might have decreased the decomposition of SOM.

The pattern observed in terms of soil amendment for available soil N and P closely mirrored that of SOM (Figs. 11a and 11b, respectively). However, the trends differed when considering the impact of climate change scenarios. Available N and P were higher under the historical climate compared to the future climates probably due to reduced precipitation, which might alter nutrient availability in the soil. Available N was notably reduced under Min-Fert in comparison to the organic amendments. Conversely, available P under Min-Fert was comparable to the organic soil amendments. Available N and P across each soil amendment in terms of future climate increased in the order SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) < SSP-1.9 (2020-2039) << SSP-8.5 (2020-2029) <<< SSP-1.9 (2080-2099).

Figure 10. Simulated daily dynamics of topsoil (0–15 cm) soil organic matter under different soil amendments and climate scenarios under a millet monocrop system in Niahkar, Senegal.

Figure 11. Simulated topsoil (0–15 cm): a) available P; b) available N; and c) SOM content at the end of ten years simulation period under different soil amendments and climate scenarios.

Figure 12. Change in topsoil (0-15 cm) soil organic matter under historical and different future climates at the end of ten years relative to the beginning of the simulation.

4.3 Model scenario output: Planting shrub density scenario

4.3.1 Aboveground biomass of *Guiera senegalensis*.

Figure 13 shows the aboveground growth dynamics of *Guiera s.* shrub during the ten-year simulation duration. The two sharp depressions within each year indicate that the shrubs were pruned twice annually.

In general, the simulated AGB of *Guiera s.* displayed an expected growth dynamic of greater AGB when planted at a higher density (PD2000) compared to a lower density (PD1000). However, this pattern was not consistent throughout the entire ten-year simulation period. In the fifth year of simulation, *Guiera s.* grown under PD1000 exhibited a higher AGB than those under PD2000, particularly under the historical, SSP-8.5 (2020-2039), and SSP-1.9 (2080-2099) climate scenarios. Interestingly, the simulated AGB for SSP-1.9 (2020-2039) and SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) showed similar results for both PD1000 and PD2000.

The simulations indicated reduced AGB under the SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) climate projection in comparison to both historical and other future climate scenarios. Likewise, the simulated AGB of *Guiera s.* was slightly increased under the SSP-1.9 (2020-2039) scenario compared to the other climate projections.

When considering the AGB of *Guiera s.* between the systems with no residue (noRR) and residue retention (RR), there were no clear distinctions observed. However, during the seventh year

under historical climate conditions, there was a slight AGB improvement in PD2000_RR compared to PD2000_noRR.

4.3.2 Crop performance of Millet under varying *Guiera s.* planting density

The impact of future climate projections on the grain yield of intercropped Millet under different planting densities of *Guiera s.* was not straightforward. Notably, the annual simulated grain yield exhibited improvement under the SSP–8.5 (2080–2099) climate projection in contrast to the other projected climates (Figure 14). In contrast, reduced grain yield was estimated for intercropped Millet under both SSP–1.9 and 8.5 near-future climate conditions. Outputs of the intercropped Millet crop performance will further be investigated and improved with data from the long-term *Piliostigma reticulatum* experiment at Kamboinse, Burkina Faso where Sorghum bicolor is intercropped with different planting densities of *P. reticulatum*.

The effect of shrub residue retention on Millet grain yield did not show any evident disparities. On the other hand, the planting density exerted an influence on the simulated grain yield production, albeit with inconsistent patterns. For example, PD2000 and PD1000 exhibited alternating higher and lower yields in relation to each other, contingent on the specific climate scenario and simulation year.

Figure 13. Simulated aboveground biomass of *Guiera s.* under different planting densities, residue retention management systems and climate scenarios over ten years.

Figure 14. Simulated grain yield of intercropped Millet under varying planting densities of *Guiera s.*, residue retention management and climate scenarios over ten years.

4.3.3 SOM under varying *Guiera s.* planting density and climate regimes

Over the course of the ten-year simulation, the dynamics of SOM exhibited an increase in SOM levels with increasing planting density for every climate scenario (Fig. 15). The LUCIA model

effectively captured the representation of *Guiera s.* biomass contributing to SOM after pruning (evident as sharp increases), as well as phases of SOM reduction due to mineralization.

The influence of *Guiera s.* residue retention on SOM was apparent solely in the context of historical climate conditions. During this period, the simulated SOM of PD2000_RR displayed higher levels compared to PD2000_noRR, and similarly, PD1000_RR exhibited an increasing pattern over PD1000_noRR. In contrast, the impact of residue retention on SOM was less pronounced under the projected future climate scenarios.

The SOM simulations at the end of the ten-year period indicated that across various planting densities and residue management approaches, the future climate projections would lead to an increase of SOM in comparison to historical conditions (Fig. 16a). Thus, while warmer temperatures generally accelerate the decomposition of organic matter, reduced water availability might decrease the activities of soil microbes hence, slowing down the decomposition process. Moreover, the simulation suggests that SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) is anticipated to contribute less to SOM compared to the other future climate scenarios. This may be due to the lower biomass inputs from shrub and crop.

The difference in SOM at the beginning and the end of the simulation as an indication of SOM build-up/ deterioration demonstrated that the existing planting density and residue management methods will enhance SOM in the future (Fig. 16b). Notably, the lower planting density coupled with the absence of residue retention (PD1000_noRR) might result in SOM deterioration under historical conditions. During this period, retaining shrub residues is crucial for bolstering SOM levels. However, in the context of future climate projections, the impact of residue retention at this planting density will not be a dominant factor in SOM enhancement.

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Figure 15. Ten years dynamics of simulated SOM under varying planting density (PD, shrubs/ha) of *Guiera s.*, residue retention (RR) system and climate projections under a under a Guiera-Millet system in Niakhar, Senegal.

Figure 16. Simulated SOM under a Guiera-Millet system in Niakhar, Senegal: a) at the end of ten years duration; and b) difference at the beginning and end of ten years duration.

4.3.4 Evapotranspiration under varying climate and planting densities

The simulated ETo exhibited a distinct pattern across climate scenarios and different planting densities of *Guiera s* (Fig. 17). There were no apparent distinctions in ETo between the various residue management approaches. Within each planting density, the SSP-8.5 (2080-2099) scenario revealed the least simulated ETo, while the highest levels were observed under SSP-1.9 (2020-2039). Evapotranspiration was greater in simulations involving PD2000 compared to PD1000, which can be attributed to the higher biomass production in the former.

Figure 17. Simulated evapotranspiration under varying planting density of *Guiera s.* and climate scenarios in ten years under a *Guiera*-Millet system in Niakhar, Senegal.

5. Conclusion and outlook

Deliverable 7.3 provides a first overview of stakeholder defined scenario outputs under long-term climate projections (climate change scenarios). The selected model scenarios from CLS systems as discussed in IP meetings and implemented by partners, focused on enhancing the system's resource use efficiency and their ability to withstand the stress of climate change. The Sob watershed in Niakhar with its well-resourced Faidherbia Flux site provided the historical weather (2018 – 2022), crop, and soil data for this modelling exercise. In developing the climate scenarios, climate projection data for the Niakhar region was obtained from GCM compilations of CMIP6 as a multi-model ensemble. Two shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), that is SSP-1.9 and SSP-8.5 for the near (2020–2039) and far (2080–2099) future were used in this exercise, allowing a rigorous assessment of the CLS systems under a spectrum of exceptionally low to a high radioactive forcing climate scenarios.

The current simulations suggested that millet AGB and grain yield production increased in the long-term under sole organic soil amendments and their combination with mineral fertilizer compared to sole mineral fertilization. This was associated with a decline in SOM under mineral fertilizer-managed soils during the ten-year simulation period. It was noted that the model needed improvements with respect to the simulation of the impact of organic residues, and hence soil cover, on soil evaporation.

With regard to climate change, a strong negative impact on millet yield, particularly during drought years and the more severe SSP-8.5 scenario, was simulated under the longer-term climate trends. For example, under the scenario SSP-8.5 (2080–2099), representing a high radioactive forcing in the far future, decreased Millet AGB was caused by shortening its growing degree-day and decreased rainfall during grain filling, which could not be compensated by the enhanced temperatures. The decline in SOM under mineral fertilizer-managed soils at the end of the simulation period relative to the beginning of the simulation was consistent in the historical and future climate scenarios. Plant available N and P replicated the pattern of SOM among the soil amendments. However, N and P were reduced under the future climates compared to the historical.

The growth dynamics of *Guiera senegalensis* at varying planting densities subjected to twice-pruning regimes and residue retention systems were well captured by the LUCIA model. Generally, the simulated AGB of *Guiera s.* was increased under the high planting density. Almost all the future climate scenarios decreased the AGB growth of *Guiera s.* compared to the historical, especially SSP – 8.5 (2080-2099). Over the course of the ten-year simulation, SOM increased with increasing *Guiera s.* planting density for every climate scenario. Interestingly, SOM decreased under historical conditions compared to the future climates. The positive contribution of residue retention to SOM was only visible under historical conditions. The reasons for these impacts need further investigations.

This long-term assessment regarding climate change resilience, productivity, and environmental impacts will be extended to the other study sites, with a particular focus on site-specific recommended CLS scenarios. The next steps will also include livestock simulation scenarios of herd management strategies to identify sustainable land use options of CLS integration in the long-term.

6. References

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